

AS AN IMPORTANT PSYCHOLOGICAL PHENOMENON OF LIFE SATISFACTION IN PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT

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Life satisfaction has a direct impact on a person's mental stability, mental state, and mood. The importance of this important event is also realized in everyday knowledge. In many scientific works, life satisfaction is interpreted as an assessment that characterizes the level of a person's life situation at the moment, rather than a simple phenomenon. When obtaining such an assessment from the respondents through a psychological and social questionnaire, it should be noted that a wide range of experiences of a person's subjective peace of mind is undoubtedly behind it.

Stability factors of a person are used different terms to describe the state of his subjective world. In particular, feeling happiness is satisfaction with life, emotional comfort, stability.

In world psychology, the problem of objective and subjective factors affecting a person's way of life, lifestyle, and life satisfaction has been studied with particular importance in the works of K.A.Abulkhanova, L.I.Antsiferova, and I.I.Djiraryan [2]. In this regard, K.A. Abulkhanova's view of the ability to realize the individual in principle, to connect his individual characteristics with the lifestyle, that is, the life strategy, is interesting. This ability of a person helps to choose and understand his stable way of life, to be able to distinguish important things from unnecessary things in personal life. One of the essences of the life strategy is to solve life problems in connection with one's personal values. This relationship was given special attention in the research of L.I. Antsiferova (1994), who studied the relationship between the individual's values, his attitude to the world and successful overcoming of difficulties. Although the factors influencing the level of life satisfaction, in particular, the value of a person, his attitude towards the world and his adaptation to it, the importance of the work is difficult to be re-evaluated in the research.

In this regard, the orientation of the meaning of life and the ability to overcome difficult life situations are dominant factors that significantly affect the level of life satisfaction. If there are external objective indicators of a person's success, that is, how effectively he works, receives a high salary, has a successful career, is respected by those around him, and is famous, then life satisfaction is an important subjective indicator of a person's success. According to M. Argayla,

satisfaction is cognitive structural happiness. This reflexive evaluation is based on the extent to which all are present and fully sustained. Life satisfaction can be understood as a product of the gap between achievement and aspiration. According to this view, too much desire prevents the feeling of satisfaction, although it is self-evident that having certain goals in life is a factor of well-being. The presence of goals in life is closely related to the feeling of satisfaction [1].

Satisfaction is a subjective assessment of one or another objects, life conditions and activities in general, life, relationships with people, and personal characteristics. A high level of life satisfaction can be called psychological comfort. Satisfaction is a very broad term with a wide range of meanings and definitions. When talking about satisfaction with life as a whole and satisfaction with a relationship with a specific person, it is necessary to express an opinion regardless of the level of importance of this person for the person.

Satisfaction can be felt from the impact of various events, depending on the level of importance for the individual. For example, the successful completion of a book that has been written for several years, and the final feelings from a delicious lunch.

For a psychologist, the uniqueness of the term "Life satisfaction" is that its ambiguity is important when evaluating subjects, that is, what exactly satisfies or dissatisfies the respondent. In most cases, subject evaluation remains out of the focus of researchers. Depending on what the respondent takes into account, whether the external aspects of life are changed only to a certain extent by his efforts, or whether his decisions, actions and activities are more important in evaluating personal achievements depends on self-evaluation.

Despite this uncertainty, it is impossible to abandon this term or completely replace it with another term, because it has an important place in the individual and mentality in society.

In the scientific and public literature on the researched topic, the phrase "emotional comfort" can be found a lot, but it is better to change it to the concept of stability. The term sustainability has a sufficiently clear meaning that its interpretation is substantially similar or consistent with everyday knowledge and norms in various scientific fields. The sense of stability and stability is very important for the subjective inner world of the person [2].

According to experts, sustainability depends more on self-esteem and sense of social belonging than on biological functions of the organism. It is related to the realization of a person's physical, mental and social potential.

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There are objective indicators of sustainability, and everyone knows at least some of them. Personal stability or the perception of other people's stability, evaluation of well-being - indicators of health, material security, success are based on objective criteria of well-being, etc. Material security affects income to one degree or another. It should be noted that this situation is to a certain extent based on the specific characteristics of the individual's attitude towards himself and the surrounding world as a whole and its individual aspects.

In any objective descriptions, all external factors of stability, according to the nature of the psyche, cannot directly affect the realization of well-being, but can only be realized through subjective perception and subjective assessment, covering all aspects of the personality.

Very strong emotional discomfort is caused by the internal reasons and reasons of the person, the power of external influences is relatively less. Rather, the reason for such a high effect is that interpersonal interaction appears as the main link regulating the social adaptation of a person who realizes the possibility of social support in the process of overcoming difficult life situations.

People who are more satisfied with their lives than others are satisfied with their health and their marital relationship. No correlation was found between the expectation of good or bad events related to the future residence and life satisfaction.

In other words, by its very nature, personality stability is primarily subjective. Objective indicators of the quality of human life may be sufficient for many economic studies, but it is important for a sociologist, for example, to take into account not only objective indicators, but also the subjective opinion of respondents in almost all studies. Undoubtedly, for a psychologist, the subjective aspects of a person's existence are of primary importance as a subject of research. It should be noted that despite the importance of subjective factors in the well-being of a person (or vice versa), the terms well-being and subjective well-being cannot be considered the same, although behind them are different but close realities [3].

In fact, the criterion of a person's life satisfaction is inextricably linked with his self-esteem system. In particular, the appearance of any positive and negative qualities in a person is definitely a sign of how satisfied he is with life.

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